

COMMUNICATIVE TEACHING OF WORDS IN PRACTICAL ENGLISH CLASSES

Nuriyeva T.

Senior teacher, Department of foreign languages, AUL, Baku

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7584315>**Abstract**

Words are the guise of our thoughts. The power of words is undeniable. Lexically, it is a speech unit, a word, which consists of a sound expression of the concept of something or an event. As the word that comes to the meaning of language and speech has been used from the past to the present, everyone will use it as much as they need in the future. As the British say, "Words are sharper than swords." ('Words cut more than swords.')

Words are the main weapon of a teacher, especially language teachers. For students learning a second language, memorizing words is a bit more difficult. How can we make our students understand the words well and use them comfortably while learning them. A student learning a foreign language must first pronounce the word in the language he is learning correctly, know its explanation, apply it to sentences, build a dialogue so that he can keep it in his memory.

Knowing a foreign language means having the ability to understand a foreign speech in that language and express one's thoughts in that language. According to these two components, which are related to each other, the tasks are carried out in a communicative way.

Using such tasks allows the teacher to introduce students to literature and art works, advise them to read the necessary works, and instill feelings of love for the Motherland and their people. Grammatical rules are mastered along with words in the given communicative tasks.

Keywords: English language, communicative task, teaching approach, task-based learning

Teach / ti:tʃ / (taught, taught / tɔ:t /)

-to give lessons to students in a school, college, university, etc.; to help sb learn sth by giving information about it.

Examples:

You were taught English last year. You are taught English. You are taught history. It's a pity you are not taught music." To teach is to learn twice." (James Britton)

Our teachers teach us.

Our teachers teach us to be good and clever.

Our teachers teach us to love our people, our language.

Our teachers teach us to love our country and to be useful to it.

Practice

1. Teach me French, please.

I cannot teach you French, I don't know French myself.

2. Look at this young teacher. Has she already taught English?

Yes, she taught us English last year.

3. I was taught to skate, but I'm a bad skater.

Well, you were taught to skate long ago and you seldom skate, that's why you are a bad skater.

Discuss /dɪ'skʌs/

-the process of discussing sb/sth; a conversation about sb/sth;

Explanation:

Discuss means talk about together, consider a problem, a question, from various points of view. You always discuss your class work with your teacher. It's useful to discuss the most interesting books you read. If some problem is important, it must be discussed and then solved.

What if we discuss some book by Jack London?

It's just the book to be discussed. Please discuss "The Gadfly" by Voynich. Please discuss "Oliver Twist" by Dickens. Please discuss "Treasure Island" by Stevenson.

Conversation

T: When I was young my favorite book was "The Gadfly" by Voynich. You have read this book, haven't you?

S: Some of us have read the book but others have not.

T: Advise your classmates to read this interesting book.

I advise you to read "The Gadfly".

It's really a wonderful book! Promise me to read it.

S: If you advise us to read it and say that it's really a wonderful book, we'll read it as soon as possible.

T: And what will you do afterwards, after all of you have read this wonderful book?

S: After all of us have read this wonderful book, we'll discuss it.

T: I'm sure you'll like Arthur, the main character in the book. He is a courageous and noble Englishman who gave his life for the freedom of Italy. You'll like him for his deep love for Father Montanelli, for his friend Gemma, and for his cause, the cause of freedom and justice.

So, what book must you borrow from the library?

S: We must borrow "The Gadfly" by Voynich from the library.

Joke /dʒəʊk /; AE /dʒoʊk /

-sth that you say or do to make people laugh, for example a funny story that you tell.

Examples:

I often tell you jokes in English.

You like me to tell you jokes, don't you?

Listen to a joke, please.

Teacher: Your Azerbaijanian exercises are always better than your English ones.

Pupil: It is because my mummy does not know English.

You see this is a joke. You are laughing.
The joke made you laugh, didn't it?

Conversation

A: Ask your classmate to tell you the best joke he knows.

B: Tell me the best joke you know, please.

C: I'm sorry, I can't tell you the best joke I know, because I'm busy now.

A: What have you asked your classmate to do?

B: I have asked my classmate to tell me the best joke he knows.

A: Has he told you the best joke he knows?

B: No, he hasn't told me the best joke he knows.

A: Why hasn't he told you the best joke he knows?

B: He hasn't told me the best joke he knows because he's busy now.

A Joke by Stevenson

They walked in the lane together

The sky was covered with stars.

They reached the gate in silence

He lifted down the bars.

She neither smiled nor thanked him

Because she knew not how.

For he was just the farmer's boy

And she the farmer's cow.

Just / dʒʌst /

-exactly; at the same moment as; no less than; equally; by a small amount;

do sth very recently; now; simply; really; completely; only.

Examples

Just so! Just now! Just listen! Just one! Just this! Just think! Just feel it! It is just the thing I want! Just nine o'clock. You are just in time. He was here just now. He has just left. They have just discussed it. We have just mended the radio set. You have just listened to my example.

Practice

1. I've got "Othello" by Shakespeare.

It's just the book I wanted.

2. I advise them to begin the job just now.

3. Will you help me, please?

Sorry, I'm busy just now.

Conversation

A: I've just got some stories by Hemingway.

B: It's just the book you wanted.

A: I don't know when to tell you this joke.

B: What if you tell it just now?

A: Will you go for a walk with me?

B: But I'm busy just now.

A: Tell me the name of the main character in "The Gadfly" please.

B: Just a moment.

Artist / 'ɑ:tɪst; AE ɑ:rt- /

-a person who creates works of art, especially paintings or drawings.

Definition

Artist is a person who practices one of the fine arts, especially painting. We know many well-known artists,

such as Leonardo da Vinci, Raphael, Sattar Behlulzade, Tahir Salahov, Repin, Gainsborough.

A person who does his work with skill and taste may be called an artist. Many writers are artists in words. They write well.

Gainsborough and Turner are both of English artists.

Practice

1. This artist is truthful.

It means that this artist always tells the truth.

2. This artist is forgetful.

It means that this artist always forgets things.

3. The artist decided to learn to play the piano.

It's wonderful of him, I will also learn to play the piano.

So, both of you, both the artist and you, are going to learn to play the piano.

Conversation

The biography of an English artist

Hogarth

William Hogarth was a great English artist. He was the first to raise British pictorial art to a level of importance. He was born in 1697 in London. The family was very large and nobody took special care of the boy.

Instead of studying he used to spend his time at their neighbour's who was an artist. The artist's studio was situated in a busy part of London, and Hogarth was able to observe life of both the rich and the poor. He dreamed of his own way in painting. He remembered the scenes and events he saw in the street and then put them into his pictures. His success he attributed to hard labour. "I know of no such thing as genius", he wrote, "genius is nothing but labour and diligence."

Hogarth painted many pictures. He is known for his drawings of scenes of life in London, Spain, Greece, China etc. He is greatly respected for the peace-loving motives in his art. [5, p.69]

Author / 'ɔ:θə(r) / noun, verb.

Definition and uses.

Author means a writer of books, stories. Nizami is the author of "Khamsa", Dickens is the author of "Oliver Twist", Tolstoy is the author of "War and Peace" etc.

There are so many good authors that I cannot say which of them is my favourite. Who is your favourite author?

Practice

1. Graham Green is the author of "The Quiet American"

2. And who is the author of "David Copperfield"?

Dickens is the author of "David Copperfield".

3. Who is the author of "The Gadfly"?

Voynich is the author of "The Gadfly"

4. Who is the author of "Hamlet"?

Shakespeare is the author of "Hamlet".

5. And who is the author of "American Tragedy"?

Dreiser is the author of "American Tragedy".

6. Is Walter Scott an English or an American author?

Walter Scott is an English author.

7. Is Henry Fielding an English or an American author?

Henry Fielding is an English author.

Conversation

T: Can you say which among the nineteenth century authors are greatest?

S: It's a pity, but I cannot say which among the nineteenth century authors are the greatest.

T: One must read a lot and be very good at English literature to say which among the nineteenth century English authors are the greatest.

What do great authors describe in their works?

S: Great authors describe the life of their people truthfully.

T: Do great authors want to see their people happy?

S: It goes without saying, great authors want to see their people happy.

Poem /'pəʊɪm; AE 'pəʊəm / - a piece of writing

Poet /'pəʊɪt; AE 'pəʊət / - a person who writes poems

Examples

Byron wrote poems. Byron is a famous English poet. We like to read poems. What poets do you like to read? Whose poems do you like to read?

Practice

1. He is reading this poem in English for the first time.

If he reads the poem for the second time, he will like it better, I think.

2. My son is reading the poem in French for the first time.

If he reads the poem for the second time, he will like it better, I think.

Conversation

Byron and Shelly are very famous in England. Everybody knows these two famous poets in Azerbaijan. I have known English since I was seven, so I can read both these poets in English. I have read and reread their poems.

T: What English poets did I speak about just now?

S: You spoke just now about Byron and Shelly.

T: They are famous in England, aren't they?

S: Yes, they are very famous in England.

Polite / pə'laɪt / adj. (politer, politest); adv. politely

(more polite and most polite are also common)

syn. courteous /'kɜ:tiəs; AE 'kɜ:rt /; opp. impolite.

Definition

A polite person is one who has good manners and respect for the feelings of others. Tarlan is polite. He always greets people, he says "Good morning", he always says "Thank you", and "Please". He offers his seat when he sees an older person standing. He never remains sitting when others are standing. He does not answer rudely. He is a polite boy. We should all be polite. Speak politely with your classmates. His politeness is well known. I like his politeness. We were all too polite to object.

Practice

1. This young is polite.

I am sure that he is a polite young.

2. Ann is not very polite when she speaks with her parents.

You must be more polite when you speak with your parents.

Conversation

"Will you be so kind as to tell me some news?" little Tom said to his elder sister.

A: In what way did little Tom ask his elder sister to tell him some news?

B: Little Tom asked his elder sister in a very polite way to tell him some news.

A: Is Tom always so polite when he speaks with his elder sister?

B: I think little Tom is always so polite when he speaks with his elder sister.

A: Does Tom's sister speak politely with Tom?

B: I am sure that Tom's sister speaks politely with Tom.

A: That's why Tom is always so polite when he speaks with his elder sister.

Both of them are very polite, aren't they?

B: Yes, both of them are very polite.

A: Should we be polite?

B: We should always be polite.

Freedom /'fri:dəm / noun.

- the right to do or say what you want without anyone stopping you.

Definition and uses.

Freedom means the state of being free. The African people are fighting for their freedom. They want to be free.

Freedom of speech. Freedom of the press. Freedom of the action.

Practice

1. People must not fight for their freedom.

Sorry, you are not right saying that people must not fight for their freedom.

2. Films never show how a man loves freedom.

Sorry, you are not right saying that films never show how a man loves freedom.

Conversation

A story

Once a woman was working. She was working hard at a report. The report was very important. She had little time. The report was to be ready in two days. The children were noisy. They wanted to play and to sing. They didn't understand that their mother was busy, that her report was important and was to be ready in two days. The woman asked the children not to be noisy. She promised to give them freedom to do what they liked in thirty minutes. [5, p.87]

Words, which are the main material of language, play an important role in conveying our ideas and thoughts during communication. In the words of the famous British linguist (Wilkins), people can describe few things without grammar, but they cannot express anything without words.

Completing these types of tasks requires constant help from the teacher. Giving the words with numerous examples, proverbs, dialogues increase the communicativeness during the lesson and creates revival in the students.

Currently, the communicative method is considered the most effective method in teaching English. The communicative method is focused on the creation of communication and the development of speaking skills on various topics. Learning a foreign language begins with learning words. Without words, there would be no language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, writing and translating. Grammatical rules are mastered along with words in the given communicative tasks.

References:

1. Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English. Oxford University Press, New 7th edition 2005.

2. Richards, Jack C. (2006). Communicative language teaching today. USA: Cambridge University Press.

3. Whong, Melinda (2011). Language Teaching: Linguistic Theory in Practice. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University.

4. Richards, Jack C.; Rodgers, Theodore S. (2014). Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. (3rd ed.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

5. Л.С.Мартиневич. Коммуникативные упражнения по Английскому языку. "Народная Асвета" Минск, 1969

EDUCATION OF AESTHETIC AND COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF SCHOOLCHILDREN IN EXTRACURRICULAR TIME

Zhantaeva M.,

Senior Lecturer of the Department "Music and Applied Arts"

M.H.Dulati Taraz Regional University,

Taraz city, Republic of Kazakhstan

Zhantaev S.

Senior Lecturer of the Department "Music and Applied Arts"

M.H.Dulati Taraz Regional University,

Taraz city, Republic of Kazakhstan

ВОСПИТАНИЕ ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКОЙ И ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ ВО ВНЕУРОЧНОЕ ВРЕМЯ

Жантаева М.К.

Старший преподаватель кафедры «Музыка и прикладное искусство»

Таразский региональный университет им. М.Х.Дулати

г.Тараз, Республика Казахстан

Жантаев С.А.

Старший преподаватель кафедры «Музыка и прикладное искусство»

Таразский региональный университет им. М.Х.Дулати

г.Тараз, Республика Казахстан

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7584336>

Abstract

This article discusses the education of aesthetic and cognitive activity of schoolchildren in extracurricular time

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается воспитание эстетической и познавательной активности школьников во внеурочное время

Keywords: aesthetics, education, cognition, activity, schoolboy, activities, extracurricular time

Ключевые слова: эстетика, воспитание, познание, активность, школьник, мероприятия, внеурочное время

Развитие воспитательной силы художественных произведений учащихся – немалая задача, выполняемая педагогами. Вместе с учениками они участвуют во внеучебной деятельности и занимаются творчеством во взаимоотношениях. Он предназначен для развития художественной деятельности и творчества учащихся, их широкого участия в нем, повышения художественного мастерства групп учащихся. В этом отношении на него будут оказыва-

ть влияние их глубокая связь с профессиональными искусствоведами, творческими союзниками, регулярные творческие встречи, советы, обмен опытом.

«Организовать воспитательную внеурочную деятельность можно различными способами. Их количество и вариативность очень разнообразно: всевозможные экскурсии, кружки, секции, круглые столы, конференции, диспуты, КВН-ы, школьные научные общества, олимпиады, школьные театры,